

Epigraphy.info VIII Workshop in Berlin

3-5 April 2024, Report from the Steering Committee

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Epigraphy.info has become an international open community pursuing a collaborative environment for digital epigraphy, which facilitates scholarly communication and interaction. It intends not to replace existing digital resources, but rather to serve as “a landing point for digital tools, practices and methodologies for managing collections of inscriptions.”¹

Webpage of the Berlin workshop: https://epigraphy.info/workshop_8/

In Berlin, from 3rd to 5th April 2024, the 8th workshop of epigraphy.info took place. Before this, other 7 workshops of the community were celebrated and generated reports:

Heidelberg: https://epigraphy.info/workshop_1/

Zadar: https://epigraphy.info/workshop_2/

Vienna: https://epigraphy.info/workshop_3/

Hamburg: https://epigraphy.info/workshop_4/

IAS (Institute of Advanced Studies) online: https://epigraphy.info/workshop_6/

Leuven: https://epigraphy.info/workshop_7/

The Berlin workshop consisted of two days of training and presentations in the Berlin-Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften and in the Humboldt Universität Berlin. It was a hybrid workshop to which 96 people (45 in person) attended.

Program / Course of the meeting

Wednesday, 3 April 2024

¹ Mission statement on the homepage of the website: <http://epigraphy.info>.

UdL – Berlin-Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Unter den Linden 8,

The first afternoon of the eighth workshop in Berlin started with a guided visit to the *Collections and the working space of CIL and IG*.

It was followed by a presentation from Matthäus Heil (BBAW, Berlin): *Digitisation of squeezes. The case of Inscriptiones Graecae* and a hands-on session led by - Eleni Bozia (U. Florida) entitled “*The Digital Epigraphy and Archaeological project: toolbox presentation.*” It promoted a lively discussion about squeezes.

To finish the day, there was an official act consisting of a welcome by the organizers and some presentations. Elena Duce Pastor (on behalf of the Steering Committee), Marietta Horster, Sebastian Prignitz (on behalf of Kaja Harter-Uibopuu), and Martin Fechner welcomed the participants. The day was concluded with a reception for all the participants hosted by the organizers.

Thursday, 4 April 2024

Humboldt Universität Berlin, Unter den Linden 6, 10099 Berlin

The day started with two parallel hands-on sessions. The first one was led by Vincent Razanajao (Paris): “*A new implementation of the Patrimonium Editor for the Late Egyptian Artefact Database: a case-study deployment and hands-on session on an eXist-db application suite*” and the second one by Jakob Jünger, Jens Borchert-Pickenhan, Mona Dorn, Markus Studer, Georg Hertkorn, Martin Riebel, Chantal Gärtner, Jörg Witzel, and Maximilian Michel (Münster, Dig. Akad. Mainz, Akad. Leipzig, Akad. Göttingen): “*Epigraf Tool: Digital Editions of Latin and German Inscriptions.*” Participants were divided into two groups according to their interests.

The second part of the morning was dedicated to project presentations. Valentina Mignosa, Maddalena Luisa Zunino, Andrea Brunello, Alessandro Locaputo, Nicola Saccomanno, and Giuseppe Serra (Udine) talked about “*Restoring lacunae in Ancient Greek Dialectical Inscriptions Using AI techniques.*” Monica Berti (Leipzig) spoke about “*Exploring Ancient Greek Authors in Digital Epigraphic Corpora*” and Rebecca Benefiel (Lexington) presented the results of “*The Ancient Graffiti Project.*”

The social media group invited the community to join them for lunch for the social media working group session. They made decisions and formulated petitions for the final meeting.

After lunch, the afternoon was divided into two parts: presentations and hands-on sessions.

The presentations were held by Georgios Tsolakis (Chicago), who spoke about “*Renewing Roman Law: Epigraphic Problems, Encoding Practices and Legal Challenges*”, and Tsvetan

Vasilev, Dimitar Iliev (Sofia), who developed the project “*ORASIS: A Digital Collection of Bulgaria’s Post-Byzantine Church Murals*”.

During the coffee break, the working group session of the Funding group took place. They invited all the members of the community to join them.

There were two parallel hands-on sessions. Participants chose between “*Using SPARQL with epigraphic RDF*” led by Imran Asif, Petra Heřmánková, Marietta Horster, and Jonathan Prag (Oxford, Mainz, Aarhus): and “*Presenting and testing AGILE, the first Lemmatizer for Ancient Greek Inscriptions*” led by Silvia Stopponi, Evelien de Graaf, and Saskia Peels-Matthey (Groningen, Leuven).

The day finished with the keynote speech of Marja Vierros (Helsinki) “*From EpiDoc XML files to a linguistically searchable corpus.*”

Most of the participants joined the conference dinner and continued to exchange ideas about their research and topics of interest.

Friday, 5 April 2024

On Friday morning, between coffees and pastries, the workshop participants had the opportunity to view and comment on the different posters presented, which are available online on the [Epigraphy.info website](https://epigraphy.info).

After an hour spent discussing the different projects submitted from all over the world, José Carlos López Gómez and Valentino Gasparini (Malaga) gave a paper titled *Connecting the Past: An Introduction to the Platform Sylloge Inscriptionum Religionis Africae Romanae (SIRAR)*. The second presentation, *The Atlas of the Landed Estates in Ancient Maghreb (ALEAM) - project Database*, was given online by Hernán González Bordasa and Alexandre Zanni (Bordeaux).

This presentation was followed by a coffee break which participants used to share ideas about the future of the community in an informal way.

During the last session of the morning, the results of the different working groups were provided.

1. Funding Group

- Update website (AP: Tom G. will take initiative on GitHub)
- Organize matchmaking (for junior and senior researchers, researchers from different domains, etc.) events (AP: Funding WG will propose a few possible dates for an online meeting).

- Publish (and update) a list of potentially interesting calls for digital epigraphy
 - Oscars open call (deadline: May 14, 2024/2nd call: October 2024): <https://oscars-project.eu/open-calls>
 - COST Action open call (deadline: October 23, 2024): <https://www.cost.eu/funding/open-call-a-simple-one-step-application-process/>
- For the new digital epigraphy research projects searching for the support of Epigraphy.info, the Funding WG can provide them with a signed version. Members of the WG with expertise in writing/supporting funding applications; current members:
 - o Lorenzo Calvelli
 - o Chiara Cenati
 - o Alberto Dalla Rosa
 - o M. Cristina de la Escosura Balbas
 - o Francisca Feraudi-Gruénais
 - o Tom Gheldof
 - o Marietta Horster

2. Social Media Group

- Change of name to “Communication and Outreach.”
- Get in touch with the Outreach group (Aaron Hershkowitz) - report of Leuven.
- The Meet-Up event in March was successful. The next one will take place in six months.

3. Vocabularies Group

- Progress made under the coordination of the FAIR Epigraphy project, see https://ontology.inscriptiones.org/type_of_inscription/ for the type of inscription vocabularies. If someone is interested in joining the next online meeting, email petra.hermankova@uni-mainz.de and they will receive an invitation and a Doodle to select the best date; the group will discuss the FAIR vocabularies poster and the next steps for the community.
- The description of the group on the website was updated to reflect the current work.

4. Ontologies Group

- The group, represented by Jonathan Prag, will be actively reaching out in the second half of 2024 with the draft proposal of the updated ontologies, FAIR Epigraphy will be active on this front.

The last part of the morning session was also dedicated to the new tasks and the election of the new members of the Steering Committee.

Topics that will be further discussed and considered (by the WGs) during this workshop are: publishing the Epigraphy.info V-VII workshop reports, updating working group descriptions on the website, organise a Digital Classicist Wiki sprint on the theme of Digital Epigraphy and setting up a Zenodo community. Before the publication of this report Petra Hermankova had already set up the Zenodo community, where this report is published, see [Epigraphy.info Community on Zenodo](#). She has also created a provisional curation policy document allowing the current Steering Committee members to be the admins of the community. Anyone can become a contributor, see the [curation policy document](#) with guidelines. The policy document should be discussed during the next meeting, but we did not want to delay the creation of the Zenodo community and the option to publish this report with a DOI.

The following committee members were elected to substitute the three resigning members until the next meeting: Marina Bastero Acha (University of Warsaw), Rebecca Benefiel (Washington and Lee University) and Georgios Tsolakis (University of Chicago); resigning members: Petra Hermankova (Aarhus University), Aaron Herskowitz (Institute for Advanced Study: Princeton) and Vincent Razanajao (Université Bordeaux Montaigne); ongoing members: Elena Duce Pastor (Autonoma University of Madrid), Jonathan Prag (Oxford University), David Eibeck (University of Mainz).

The next workshop will be held in [Aarhus \(Denmark\)](#) 2 - 4 April 2025; the organizer of the next workshop is Petra Hermankova (Aarhus University), Denmark.

Finally, three suggestions were made by the participants with a view to the next workshop:

- More time for working groups meetings during the Workshop.
- More time for poster presentations.
- Seeking a source of financial support for doctoral students attending the workshop.

For more information and suggestions visit our website [Epigraphy.info](#), follow us on Twitter ([@epigraphy_info](#)) and Facebook ([Epigraphy.info](#)). If you want to become a member of the community and join the working groups, write an email to info@epigraphy.info.

Madrid - Warsaw - Aarhus, June 2024